

**RESEARCH COMPETENCIES AND PERCEIVED DIFFICULTIES ENCOUNTERED
BY GRADE 12 STUDENTS IN THESIS WRITING AT NATIONAL UNIVERSITY
BULACAN INCORPORATED: A BASIS FOR DEVELOPMENT OF
CAPACITY ENHANCEMENT PROGRAM**

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ABSTRACT

As part of learners' curriculum, completion of a thesis has always been perceived as a challenge. Even though writing is one of the core academic skills being taught from primary level, academic paper is different. Several studies showed factors affecting thesis writing. This led the researchers to conduct this study utilizing descriptive comparative research design to review the association and differences between research competencies and perceived difficulties in thesis writing. The researchers selected two hundred eight (208) Grade 12 students from STEM, ABM, and HUMSS strands through stratified random sampling method. Based on the results of the study, it was revealed that there is a highly significant difference in the information seeking ($F=18.7$; $p=0.001$) and methodology skills ($F=30.0$; $p=0.001$) of the students. Moreover, it showed that respondents have significant differences in terms of personality ($F=5.3$; $p=0.01$) and linguistic factors ($F=5.56$; $p=0.048$). Findings also revealed significant association between personality factors (Pearson = -0.141 ; -0.257) and sociocultural (Pearson = -0.214 ; -0.304) with research competencies. This implies that as the research skills of the Grade 12 students improve, it would greatly help them in minimizing the challenges in completing thesis writing. The researchers look forward to this study being utilized as a useful reference by future researchers who would be exploring further the connections between research competencies and perceived difficulties in thesis writing. The researchers recommend looking further on sociocultural and its effect on thesis writing. Lastly, an interview to extend the clarity of the data from survey questionnaires.

Keywords - *thesis writing, personality factors, sociocultural factors, linguistic factors, research skills, research competency*

INTRODUCTION

Thesis-writing gives students a chance to contribute new findings to their areas of concentration and is a significant element of academic achievement. This course involves literature evaluation, data collecting, data analysis, as well as having a well-established research question or hypothesis for conducting a deep study of a certain topic. Organizing a thesis involves planning, presentation and orderly development and presentation of the ideas, arguments, and results. It is a record of the subject areas studied by a student where the student can also demonstrate his or her capability of studying individually as well as showing rationality and communication skills. Thesis writing provides definite skills that are useful in students' further academic and occupational progress.

National University has been recognized as a research and teaching institution. In a recent final research defense in Practical Research 2 subject, 13 out of 14 groups got high scores in usage of statistical treatment, grammar and spelling, review of literature, and data gathering. However, the researchers could not remove in the picture the actual experiences of the students while conducting the study. It includes choosing the right topic, looking at related studies, proper choosing of methodologies to be used, writing in a thematic manner, incorrect format and even issues within researchers' collaboration. Thesis writing challenges among Master students and he concluded that even these Palestinian MA students have difficulties in 1. Selecting appropriate topic; 2. Methodology Skills; 3. Linguistic and Writing issues; 4. Lack of confidence in writing; 5. Citation and Documentation challenges; 6. Insufficient feedback; and 7. Limited resources (Abu Alyan, 2022). With this, the researchers decided to look into these aspects further.

One of the four macro skills in language is writing. Writing skills do not just include the physical act of writing. Skills like researching, planning and outlining, editing, revising, spelling and grammar, and organization are critical components of the writing process (Kaplan, 2024). Also, writing is a necessary skill in the modern world. Most people have a mobile device that they use for e-mailing, social media, as an alarm clock to start the day, reading the news, searching for information, ordering food, managing transportation (e.g., monitoring traffic, accessing public transit), or for relaxing pursuits, such as watching a movie or listening to music. However, many students struggle with composing longer prose, especially for academic tasks (Dunn, 2021) .

In the educational field, academic writing may include essays, research papers or thesis, reports and so on. In actuality, most of the studies show difficulty mainly in academic writing. Conducting a research or writing thesis is conducted globally to address opportunities or to answer questions that are significant to different fields. In general, an academic paper like writing research seeks to answer certain questions which so far have not been answered or studied already but the outcomes may change depending on circumstances. In the study of Earl Robert Babbie, research is a systematic inquiry to

describe, explain, predict, and control the observed phenomenon (Qiu, Qui, and Zeng, 2022).

In line with this, academic writing needs a lot of study time and practice in order to develop learners' writing skill (Oshima and Houge, 2023). Also, research does not come without its challenge from exploring new ideas to discussions of findings (Chartier, 2023). Conducting a research study is a difficult task where students have to acquire a deeper knowledge in the target field and plan the study according to a fitting research objectives and methodologies (Qasem & Zayid, 2019).

Additionally, lacking local learning experiences, difference in learning expectations, and social isolation (Ma, 2020). Locally, it is pointed out that challenges include difficulties in research and statistical tools, expressing knowledge and ideas, identifying relevant research problems, and writing literature reviews (Pangket, 2023). Moreover, when it comes to the difficulties faced by thesis writers, money plays an important role in practically all attempts. Communication, limited resources, and presenting ideas are all frequent financial issues (Natividad-Franco, 2022). As proposed in Sound Writing, The Six-Step Process was established which focuses on articulating of ideas, gathering of knowledge, identifying patterns, formulating questions that respond to the prompt, listening to evidence, and developing a working thesis. A working thesis is essential in the early stages of writing because it helps you read selectively, in the same way that your issue-based question guides your inquiry. Reading raises questions, helping you see what you know and need to know, and challenging you to read on (Chun et.al, 2020).

Learners might have engaged in thesis writing without knowing the basic factors or what difficulties may face in the process of completion. It might be the students' personality factors itself, or their society and cultural factors, or even the linguistic factors. Nevertheless, in order to reveal the difficulties in research writing, further research of the factors on the difficulties of writing thesis is needed. Therefore, this research would like to analyze the differences in research competencies and perceived difficulties encountered by Grade 12 students. In addition, the researchers will look into the association of research competencies and perceived difficulties in thesis writing. The findings of the researchers will aid in proposing a research capacity enhancement program. This program is targeted support that is suited to the students' challenges, enhancing academic support systems, and strengthening students' research abilities.

Review of Related Literature

Information Seeking Skills

These skills are important for academic success, professional development, and personal decision-making. Information-seeking is driven by recognizing an information gap or a specific information need. These skills can enhance chances of finding relevant and reliable information. Hence, these are the following methods of information seeking (1) online search; (2) library research; (3) expert consultation; (4) peer communication; (5) literature review; (6) observation and experiment; (7) professional networks and

conference; and (8) social media and online communities. The best results are frequently obtained by combining several methods to increase knowledge, make well-informed judgments, and remain up to date with the most recent advancements in the areas of interest (Md. Ashikuzzaman, 2023). Moreover, the effective information seeking such as intelligent searching, critical source evaluation, and systematic organization tends to have a high academic achievement (Weber et al., 2018).

Methodology Skills

These skills are necessary for conducting research, gathering and analyzing data, and approaching problems systematically. These are part of the research where the researcher finds confusion to assess the appropriate methodology used in their research paper. Students find it difficult to apply in designing experiments, collecting data, and applying statistical analysis. Appropriate methodology used in research is essential to ensure reliability and validity of the results (Diocos, 2022). An appropriate methodology helps control for any biases, provides a clear framework for data collection and analysis, and ensures the reliability and accuracy of the results. It enables researchers to methodically approach study issues and hypotheses, improving the generalization and the consistency of the results (Hassan, 2024).

Linguistic Factors in Thesis Writing

From that, the most difficulties that the students found in their writing thesis are related to their English proficiency is still low and limited (Lestari, 2020). Hence, that becomes the first cause that they cannot develop their writing thesis well. Most of the students are having difficulty in using English grammar, choosing the right vocabulary, spelling, and punctuation correctly (Fitria, 2022). It is also reported that language proficiency emerged as a main difficulty like avoiding grammatical errors, unfamiliarity with specific terms (Farizawati, Cendana & Nuraiza, 2024).

Personal Factors Thesis Writing

These factors have a crucial role in thesis writing. Individual student traits have a vital role in navigating the challenging process of writing a thesis. These traits include intrinsic motivation, self-efficacy, time management, and prior research experience. Students with high intrinsic motivation in their abilities were more likely to persevere through challenges (Criado-Davila et al. 2024) or it could be due to poor self-esteem (Farizawati, Cendana & Nuraiza, 2024). Moreover, one of the key reasons causing challenges in writing a thesis is the students' lack of conceptual understanding about the necessary learning. The participants showed that they lacked critical thinking, applied theory skills, and had failed to establish the limits of a research problem while selecting a research topic. They also struggled to choose the right research strategy, method, and data gathering tools according to (Ameen et.al, 2019). In addition, the difficulties of writing a thesis include inappropriateness in presenting different chapters of the research and lack of academic writing skills (Rizwan, 2022).

Sociocultural Factors Thesis Writing

It is said that students tend to have difficulty in understanding the culture department of the university or the educational institution regarding the format of thesis

writing. This contributes to the misalignment and multiple revisions (Puspita, 2021). Also, sociocultural issues affect the students in thesis writing. Cultural norms and expectations, such as adherence to established frameworks that may hinder creativeness, have an impact on undergraduates' academic methods and cause them to struggle with writing their theses. Furthermore, students' readiness and confidence in writing are influenced by their educational backgrounds, which are affected by their cultural preferences (Rizwan, 2022). Additionally, learners may collaborate and help each other in editing, revising, and improving their academic papers through peer discussion (Motlhaka, 2020). Academic deficiency could be due to lack of some academic writing skills and their limited knowledge about thesis writing and research whereas the socio-cultural barriers are lack of support from supervisor and from the family, lack of cooperation of the sample for the research, and insufficient academic background (Bakhou & Bouhania, 2020)

Calibration is associated with learning and performance. Hence, there is a need for school institutions and teachers to offer strategies and tools to assist students improve their writing skills. For example, it helps if the teacher offers a rubric or a description of the required components, as well as some examples of high- and low-quality examples. In this case, a parameter of what should and should not be done is set. Teachers should consider the characteristics of each learner when providing intervention to address the motivational and writing skill challenges of students, such as the planning stage of writing a research. Jotting down notes of each idea can greatly assist. Some writers like to use graphic organizers to define key ideas, and then sub points or examples. This may give students an illustration of what they should do to the next steps (Kolovelonis, 2024).

This study was anchored on constructivism theory by Jean Piaget and Lev Vygotsky. This theory highlights that knowledge is constructed by individuals based on their experiences and interactions with the world. Based on Piaget's theory, children acquire knowledge at different stages of cognitive development through interactions with their surroundings. Moreover, Vygotsky's theory emphasizes the social component of learning, social interaction and cultural context are essential for the development of cognitive abilities. These two theories support the idea of learners actively engaging in their own learning process. (Constructivism Learning Theory & Philosophy of Education, 2024)

In this modern era that advancement of research is becoming a trend and being focused by educational institutions, it is essential to determine what are the challenges encountered by the students. Identify if the teachers are knowledgeable about it and what are the initiatives they do. Given that there are tools that may be used for efficient thesis writing, teachers must focus as well in helping students on their vocabulary and language skills as these skills are fundamental in starting and finishing of their academic writing.

Conceptual Framework

The framework represents the summary of the research that explains the processes involved. This directs the researchers in coming-up with a series of actions required in the entire duration of the given educational research.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Research Questions

This study aims to explore the differences in research competencies and encountered difficulties in thesis writing and the association between the mentioned variables of Grade 12 students of STEM, HUMSS, and ABM at National University Bulacan during the Academic Year 2023 – 2024.

Specifically, this research aims to address the following research questions:

1. How may the research competencies be described by the students in terms of:
 - 1.1 Information seeking; and
 - 1.2 Methodology skills?
2. How may the students perceived difficulties in thesis writing be described in terms of:
 - 2.1 Personality;
 - 2.2 Socio cultural; and
 - 2.3 Linguistics?
3. Are there significant differences on the research competencies and perceived difficulties in thesis writing among the strands?
4. Is there a significant association between students' research competencies and perceived difficulties in thesis writing?
5. What capacity enhancement program can be developed based on the result of the study?

Hypotheses

This study was guided and tested by the following hypotheses:

There is no significant association between students' research competencies and perceived difficulties in thesis writing.

There is no significant difference between the research competencies and perceived difficulties in thesis writing among Grade 12 STEM, HUMSS and ABM strands.

Significance of the Study

The purpose of the study was to explain the differences in research competencies and perceived difficulties encountered by Grade 12 students in thesis writing and look into the association between the said variables. The research findings may help the

students be knowledgeable of the opportunities they have in thesis writing. Hence, could focus on addressing it. As for teachers, they may use this as a basis of which to focus on and elaborate during research classes. This may offer important insights about how a student's completion of a thesis is affected by the thesis writing research competencies and perceived difficulties. These results may be used by educational institutions to initiate a prescribed action to better meet and further improve students' thesis writing ability. Lastly this study may provide insights to future researchers on ideas about the research gap and may use the capacity enhancement plan in the next study.

METHODOLOGY

Locale of the Study

Figure 1. Map of Baliuag, Bulacan. Uploaded by RMN Network on April 23, 2020

Figure 2. NU Bulacan Incorporated. Uploaded by NU Baliuag at wikimapia on 2020

This study was conducted at NU Bulacan Incorporated. It is located at SM Baliuag Complex, Doña Remedios Trinidad, Highway, Brgy. Pagala, Baliuag, Bulacan, Philippines, 3006.

Respondents and Sampling

The respondents in this study are the Senior High School Students of National University Bulacan Incorporated. The study aims to investigate the differences in research competencies of the Grade 12 STEM, HUMSS, and ABM students and perceived difficulties in thesis writing. Moreover, the researchers also analyzed the association between research competencies and perceived difficulties in thesis writing. In gathering the total number of respondents in this study, the researchers utilized Raosoft Calculator with a 5% margin of error and 95% confidence level. The researchers came up with a total of 208 samples and this was equally distributed as follows: STEM (319 : 147); HUMSS (55 : 25); and ABM (77 : 36).

The respondents were selected using stratified random sampling techniques in which the population of Grade 12 students were stratified based on strands then used proportionate sampling to maintain correct representations from each strand.

Research Design

This study utilized the non-experimental quantitative research design. Specifically, the descriptive evaluation, comparative, and correlational were used. Descriptive evaluation was employed to describe the research competencies of the students in terms of information seeking agreement and methodology skills satisfactory. This was also applied to describe the students' perceived difficulties in thesis writing in terms of personality, socio-cultural, and linguistics. Additionally, descriptive comparative quantitative research design was used to assess the significant differences on the research competencies and perceived difficulties in thesis writing among the strands. Lastly, descriptive correlational quantitative research design was utilized to determine the significant association between students' research competencies and perceived difficulties in thesis writing.

The subject of the study will be selected Grade 12 Senior High School students from the National University Bulacan Incorporated. The teachers are not included as the researchers would like to focus on the side of learners. Two adopted survey questionnaires were used from Natividad-Franco, V. (2022) and Meerah, et.al (2012). The questionnaires included the statements about information seeking skills, methodology skills, personal, social, and linguistic factors. The questionnaires will be uploaded in google form. Descriptive statistics like weighted mean and standard deviation were used to analyze the data gathered. The researchers did not conduct a post interview due to limited time allocated for completing the study, a relatively important source of insights that could support the analyzed numerical data. Hence, triangulation was not administered.

Data Gathering Procedures

The researchers looked for standardized questionnaires for research competencies and perceived difficulties in thesis writing. These were validated by the research professor to ensure alignment on the objectives of the study. Secondly, the researchers submitted a letter of request to conduct the study and request for the population of the target respondents. Upon the receipt of the approval of the letter from the Schools Academic Office, the data-gathering procedure in the participating Senior High School Strands commenced. The researchers administered the questionnaires using Google Form to the respondents through Facebook Messenger Group Chats and a consent and assent letter were used and a clear instruction was indicated before the actual instrument. The gathered responses were checked if it had satisfied the required number of samples.

Instrumentations

This study utilized the two different Likert-scale instruments to assess the students' research competencies and perceived difficulties in thesis writing.

Research Skills

To identify the research competencies of Grade 12 students, the researchers adopted the 5 point Likert Scale instruments crafted by Meerah, et.al (2012) on the study entitled “Developing an Instrument to Measure Research Skills” which is divided into two parts; Information Seeking Skills (26 items) and Methodology Skills (13 items). The reliability of the scale was measured through Cronbach’s alpha that resulted in reliability ranging from 0.78 – 0.93.

Perceived Difficulties in Thesis Writing

Second survey-questionnaire was adopted from study of Natividad-Franco (2022) entitled “Difficulties and challenges of Library and Information Science students in thesis writing during the pandemic” but was adapted by Natividad-Franco from Puspita (2019) which focuses on the learners’ difficulties in Thesis writing in terms of Personality (19 items), Socio-Cultural (7 items), and Linguistic Factors (4 items). The three factors are measured through 5-point Agreement Likert Scale. The reliability of the scale was measured through Cronbach’s alpha that resulted in .945, .924, and .919 for personality, sociocultural, and linguistic factors respectively.

Data Analysis

The data gathered from research competencies and perceived difficulties in thesis writing were tabulated in Jamovi, a statistical spreadsheet software. Descriptive statistics were applied in analyzing the responses including frequency, weighted mean and standard deviation. The mean and standard deviation were utilized to describe the information seeking, methodology skills, personality factors, sociocultural factors and linguistic factors. It is further analyzed using inferential statistics, specifically, One-way Analysis of Variance was used to determine if there are significant differences between research competencies of the Grade 12 Students from STEM, HUMSS and ABM including the differences on their perceived difficulties in thesis writing. Multiple regression analysis was employed to determine the significant association between students’ research competencies and perceived difficulties in thesis writing.

RESULTS

In this study, 147, 25, and 36 respondents from Grade 12 STEM, HUMSS, and ABM, respectively, were included in descriptive and inferential analyses. The results aimed to assess and compare the differences between the personalities and social behavior of each birth order and to determine any statistically significant differences experienced by these birth orders. One-Way ANOVA was implemented individually on personality and birth order to find the significance level and a post-hoc analysis was conducted to provide specific differences between the different birth order positions and the different personalities and social behaviors.

Table 1. Total Mean of Research Competencies

Skills	STEM		ABM		HUMSS	
Information Seeking	3.977	A	3.790	A	4.149	A
Methodological	3.958	S	3.390	SS	4.169	S
<i>Legend:</i>	<i>Rating Scale</i>		<i>Description</i>			
	1.00-1.80		Strongly Disagree (SD)		Very Poor (VP)	
	1.81-2.60		Disagree (D)		Poor (P)	
	2.61-3.40		Neither Agree nor Disagree (N)		So so (SS)	
	3.41-4.20		Agree (A)		Satisfactory (S)	
	4.21-5.00		Strongly Agree (SA)		Very Satisfactory (VS)	

Table 1 presents the total mean scores for research competencies, including information-seeking and methodological skills, across the STEM, ABM, and HUMSS strands. HUMSS garnered the highest mean (4.149) with the verbal interpretation of “Agree” while ABM garnered the lowest mean of (3.790) with the verbal interpretation of “Agree”. Moreover, in terms of methodological skills, HUMSS garnered the highest mean of (4.169) which was interpreted as satisfactory while ABM garnered the lowest mean of (3.390) which was interpreted as So so (SS). Furthermore, STEM students remained in between ABM and HUMSS strands.

Table 2. Total Mean of Perceived Difficulties in Thesis Writing

	STEM		ABM		HUMSS	
Personality Factors	2.974	N	3.031	N	2.808	N
Socio Cultural Factors	2.715	N	2.813	N	2.606	N
Linguistic Factors	2.816	N	2.986	N	2.600	D
<i>Legend:</i>	<i>Rating Scale</i>		<i>Description</i>			
	1.00-1.80		Strongly Disagree (SD)			
	1.81-2.60		Disagree (D)			
	2.61-3.40		Neither Agree nor Disagree (N)			
	3.41-4.20		Agree (A)			
	4.21-5.00		Strongly Agree (SA)			

Table 2 shows the overall mean of students’ perceived difficulties among strands in thesis writing. Among strands, the students find neither agree nor disagree from the perceived difficulties such as personality factors, socio-cultural, and linguistic factors in thesis writing. ABM strands garnered the highest mean among the perceived difficulties factors while HUMSS garnered the lowest perceived difficulties factors in thesis writing.

Table 3. Regression Analysis of Research Competencies and Difficulties in Thesis Writing

		Pearson	p	Interpretation	Decision
	Information Seeking	-0.141	0.042	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
<i>Personality Factors</i>	Methodology	-0.257	0.001	Highly Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis

	Information Seeking	-0.214	0.002	Highly Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
<i>Sociocultural Factors</i>	Methodology	-0.304	0.001	Highly Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
	Information Seeking	-0.113	0.104	Not Significant	Accept the Null Hypothesis
<i>Linguistic Factors</i>	Methodology	-0.130	0.061	Not Significant	Accept the Null Hypothesis

Table 3 shows the regression analysis of research competencies and difficulties in thesis writing. The calculated p-values for information seeking and methodology in personality factors (0.042 and 0.001) and socio-cultural factors (0.002 and 0.001) are less than the alpha value (0.05). This indicates that personality factors and socio-cultural factors are significantly associated with research competencies. Consequently, the null hypothesis is rejected, signifying highly significant associations between research competencies and personality as well as socio-cultural factors. However, the calculated p-values for information seeking and methodology in linguistic factors (0.104 and 0.061) are greater than the alpha value (0.05). This means that research competency skills are not significantly associated with linguistic factors. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted, indicating no significant association between research competencies and linguistic factors.

Table 4. *One-Way Analysis of Variance of Research Competencies*

Groups	F	P	Interpretation	Decision
Information Seeking Skills	18.70	0.001	Highly Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Methodology Skills	30.00	0.001	Highly Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis

Note. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, $p < 0.001$

Table 4 shows the one-way analysis of variance of research competencies among the STEM, ABM, and HUMSS strands. Both information seeking and methodological skills have a p-value of 0.001, which is less than the alpha value of 0.05. This implies that research competencies are highly significantly different among the STEM, ABM, and HUMSS strands. Consequently, the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating highly significant differences in information seeking and methodological skills among the STEM, ABM, and HUMSS strands in thesis writing.

To further check which strands differ significantly from one another, a post hoc analysis was conducted. The results revealed that information seeking skills and methodological skills of STEM (M=3.98 / 3.96; SD=0.227 / 0.124), ABM (M=3.79 / 3.74; SD=0.198 / 0.118), and HUMSS (M=4.15 / 4.17; SD=0.224 / 0.165) yielded p-values less

than 0.05. This indicates that there are significant differences in research competencies among the strands.

Table 5. *One-Way Analysis of Variance of Perceived Difficulties in Thesis Writing*

Groups	F	P	Interpretation	Decision
Personality Factors	5.30	0.010	Highly Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Sociocultural Factors	3.29	0.077	Not Significant	Accept the Null Hypothesis
Linguistic Factors	5.56	0.048	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis

Note. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, $p < 0.001$

Table 5 shows the one-way analysis of variance of students' perceived difficulties in thesis writing. The calculated p-value for personality factors (0.01) is less than the alpha value (0.05). This means that the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating a significant difference in personality factors among the STEM, ABM, and HUMSS strands in thesis writing. Moreover, the p-value for linguistic factors (0.048) is also less than the alpha value (0.05). Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, signifying significant differences in linguistic factors among the strands in thesis writing. However, for socio-cultural factors, the calculated p-value (0.077) is greater than the alpha value (0.05). This indicates that the null hypothesis is not rejected, signifying no significant differences in socio-cultural factors among the strands in thesis writing.

To confirm these results, a post hoc analysis was conducted. In terms of personality factors, the difference between STEM and ABM ($p = 0.681$) is regarded as insignificant. On the other hand, socio-cultural factors revealed significant differences only between ABM and HUMSS ($p = 0.020$). Lastly, difficulties in linguistic factors indicate significant differences only between ABM and HUMSS ($p = 0.014$).

Table 6. *Proposed Capacity Enhancement Program (RCEP)*

Component	Objective	Strategy	Person Responsible	Budget
DAY 1 Chapter 1: <i>Introduction</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Understand the organization of chapter 1 ● Determine a research problem ● Craft the research questions ● Identify 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Browse through assignments and activities for topic inspiration ● Create mind map of what interests me ● Write objectives then amend based on feedback 	Research Instructors and Strand Coordinators	Php.300

	independent and dependent variables	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Guide for writing thesis title 		
DAY 2 Chapter 2: <i>Review of the Related Literature</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Understand the thematic organization of RRLs ● Utilize proper transitional devices in sentence construction. ● Cite references format ● Avoid plagiarism 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Refresh information seeking skills ● Grammar Practice ● Introduction of online databases like Google Scholar, ERIC, Scopus and Research Gate. ● Paraphrasing and Citation Worksheets 	Research Instructors and English Teachers	Php.1000
DAY 3 Chapter 3: <i>Research Method</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Determine the research design, proper statistical tool, and sampling techniques ● Write a research instrument ● Understand data gathering from dissemination of questionnaires to collecting responses. ● Familiarize common statistical tools and data measurement scales 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Critique proposed methodology ● Amend proposed research instruments based on feedback and alignment on research questions. ● Problem Solving through Statistical Tools ● Introduction of Google / MS forms 	Research Instructors and Statistics Teachers	Php.300
DAY 4 Chapter 4:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Presentation, Analyzation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Incorporation of statistical 	Research Instructors	Php. 1000

<i>Results and Discussion</i>	and Interpretation of data	software like Jamovi, SPSS, Raosoft and Microsoft Excel ● Data Analysis Activities	and Statistics Teachers	
DAY 5 Chapter 5: <i>Conclusion and Recommendations</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Write conclusion ● Analyze what can be improved on the study 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Presentation of examples ● Practice writing skills 	Research Instructors and Principal	Php.500

The results of the study may be an important baseline for the future researchers. However, the identified strands were limited as these were the only offered programs at National University, future studies may consider looking into ICT, GAS, HE and other strands. Extending the possible aid of the results in future studies, the researchers crafted a proposed Research Capacity Enhancement Program (RCEP).

Research Advising and Paneling Advocates (RAPA)

Selected teachers from the Senior High School department are encouraged to be part of Research Advising and Paneling Advocates (RAPA). This committee is mainly composed of research instructors, linguistics and mathematics teachers. They will act as overall in charge of the Research Capacity Enhancement Program. Furthermore, they will design the plan, coordinate with other departments, monitor and evaluate the results. and supervise the overall implementation. These advocates will be the same teachers to sit as research panelists and research advisers throughout the school year to ensure alignment and linear advising.

DISCUSSION

Based on the results from addressing the research problem, this study has revealed several significant findings.

1. All strands agreed on having strong information-seeking skills, with HUMSS students achieving the highest mean scores According to the study by Pabustan et al. (2024), students in the HUMSS strand possess robust information-seeking and communication skills. This strand naturally emphasizes communication skills such as speaking, writing, and critical thinking, which contribute to greater proficiency in these areas. Furthermore, all strands demonstrated satisfactory levels in methodological skills, with HUMSS students obtaining the highest mean scores. This indicates that HUMSS students exhibit superior methodological skills compared to their STEM and ABM students. This contrasts with the findings of Monica et al. (2020), which suggest that brain dominance plays a significant role

in shaping students' academic preferences and has a substantial impact on their future educational and professional trajectories. The STEM curriculum, which emphasizes analytical, logical, and critical thinking skills associated with left-brain dominance, contrasts with the HUMSS curriculum that caters to right-brained students, who tend to exhibit creativity and artistic abilities. In contrast, ABM students recorded the lowest mean scores in both information-seeking and methodological skills. This suggests that ABM students lack confidence in these two skills related to thesis writing. This finding contrasts with Gepila Jr. et al. (2022), who reported that ABM students demonstrate good methodological skills, particularly in effective data interpretation and basic problem-solving. However, their study also revealed challenges with critical thinking and innovative problem-solving, especially in real-world business contexts.

2. Overall mean of students' perceived difficulties in thesis writing. Among the STEM, HUMSS, and ABM strands, students have neutral positions regarding personality factors, socio-cultural factors, and linguistic factors. This implies that students in these strands neither agree nor disagree with these factors as difficulties in thesis writing. HUMSS has the lowest mean in all factors, indicating that students in this strand experience fewer difficulties in thesis writing, particularly in linguistic factors, compared to STEM and ABM. The nature of the HUMSS curriculum aids in improving students' communication skills. The curriculum's emphasis on understanding and analyzing a variety of social, cultural, and ethical concerns helps develop students' diverse perspectives and enhances their ability to express complex concepts (Pabustan et al., 2024).
3. The calculated p-values for information seeking and methodology in personality factors and socio-cultural factors are less than the alpha value. The null hypothesis is rejected, signifying highly significant associations between research competencies and personality as well as socio-cultural factors. As research competency skills increase, the perceived difficulties in thesis writing decrease. This finding is supported by the study of Aristya, Sabarun, and Siminto (2024), which mentioned that personality traits significantly affect the ability to write effectively, organize, and structure sentences. Additionally, poor self-esteem (Farizawati, Cendana, & Nuraiza, 2024) and comprehension of research methods and chapter 4 (Fitria, 2022) are primarily linked to difficulties in writing a thesis. However, the calculated p-values for information seeking and methodology in linguistic factors are greater than the alpha value. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted, indicating no significant association between research competencies and linguistic factors. This contrasts with the study by Fitria (2022), which stated that learners tend to have difficulty using English grammar, choosing the right vocabulary, and correctly applying spelling and punctuation when completing a thesis.
4. Both information seeking and methodological skills have a p-value, which is less than the alpha value. This implies that research competencies are highly significantly different among the STEM, ABM, and HUMSS strands. Consequently, the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating highly significant differences in information seeking and methodological skills among the STEM, ABM, and

HUMSS strands in thesis writing. The post hoc analysis also supports that there are significant differences in research competencies among the strands.

5. The calculated p-value for personality factors is less than the alpha value. This means that the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating highly significant differences in personality factors among the STEM, ABM, and HUMSS strands in thesis writing. This finding aligns with Puspita's (2019) study, which stated that confidence is indeed a driver of difficulties in thesis writing. Moreover, the p-value for linguistic factors is also less than the alpha value. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, signifying significant differences in linguistic factors among the strands in thesis writing. However, for socio-cultural factors, the calculated p-value is greater than the alpha value. This implies that the null hypothesis is accepted, signifying no significant differences in socio-cultural factors among the strands in thesis writing. Post hoc analysis confirms all strands have significant differences among research competencies and perceived difficulties in thesis writing.

Conclusions

This study aims to evaluate the research competency and perceived difficulties among grade 12 STEM, ABM, and HUMSS students in thesis writing. Hence, these are the drawn conclusion of the researchers:

1. Among the different strands, HUMSS students demonstrate more proficient information-seeking and methodological skills compared to their STEM and ABM counterparts. Conversely, ABM students show a lack of confidence in both information-seeking and methodological skills. Research competency skills may be developed depending on the nature of the strand.
2. All strands maintain a neutral stance regarding difficulties related to personality, socio-cultural, and linguistic factors in thesis writing. The research indicates that HUMSS students experience fewer difficulties compared to STEM and ABM students, particularly in relation to linguistic factors.
3. There is a significant association between research competency skills and both personality and socio-cultural factors across all strands. This suggests that as students' research competency skills improve, their perceived difficulties related to personality and socio-cultural factors decrease. However, no significant association is found between research competency skills and linguistic factors across the strands.
4. Research competencies differ significantly among strands. Additionally, perceived difficulties related to personality and linguistic factors show significant differences among the strands, while socio-cultural factors do not exhibit significant differences.
5. The researchers crafted a proposed program entitled "Research Capacity Enhancement Program based on the findings of the study which shows that all strands have significantly different research competencies and perceived difficulties level. This program will help the students to learn holistically and improve their information-seeking and methodological skills simultaneously.

Recommendations

The study adds information on abilities of different senior high school strands in terms of academic writing. The researchers look forward to this study being utilized as a useful reference by future researchers who would be exploring further the connections between research competencies and perceived difficulties in thesis writing. To obtain beneficial data, the researchers recommend adapting standardized instruments but legally modify the contents if needed, stick on using 4 point likert scale and abandon the inclusion of neutral scale to get a clearer view of what the respondents are experiencing. Research further on association between linguistic factors and methodology skills. Furthermore, sociocultural factors are revealed having association with perceived difficulties, therefore it is recommended to look at what is the best way to divide students into groups of researchers; be it teacher's choice or students' choice. Lastly, the researchers recommend conducting a post interview with the respondents to help explain the numerical data.

Compliance with Ethical Considerations

Since selected students at National University Bulacan Incorporated were needed, some ethical issues were discussed. The researchers seek the following letters of approval: first letter to conduct the study at NU Bulacan Incorporated, second, letter for data privacy act, lastly letter for the respondents. The researcher considered the following factors that are required to protect participants' privacy and safety from ethical concerns that will be taken into account during the research process, such as confidentiality and consent. In accordance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, also known as RA 10173, all responses provided by respondents will be kept private and utilized exclusively for academic purposes. The researchers provided the chosen respondents with crucial information about the study, such as its goal and purpose, in order to obtain their consent. Additionally, the respondents will be informed that they are under no obligation to continue with the research and can back out at any time which is included in google forms. By withholding the participants' names and other personal information from the research, the participants' confidentiality will also be guaranteed. The questionnaire only inquired about pertinent information that aided in addressing the research questions. The findings will be interpreted as what results may be revealed based on the gathered data. After the analyses and interpretation of data, the raw responses are no longer needed to be stored, hence, the researchers deleted the file and google form link.

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